

Osmium(VIII)-catalysed Oxidation of Dimethylamine by Periodate in Aqueous Alkaline Medium

S. C. HIREMATH^a, S. A. CHIMATADAR^{*b} and J. R. RAJU^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Arts and Science College, Jamkhandi

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad-580 003

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A few attempts have been made in the field of oxidation of aliphatic amines in acidic¹ and alkaline² media. The oxidation of simplest dialkyl amine, i.e. dimethylamine (DMA) in alkaline medium is limited by the fact that it is a gas at ordinary temperature. Few attempts have been made in gaseous medium³ to oxidise DMA but no study seems to be available in alkaline medium. This, stimulated us to investigate oxidation of DMA in alkaline medium.

Results and Discussion

Kinetic runs were carried out at excess of DMA with conditions as shown in Table 1. At different initial IO_4^- concentrations, the plots of $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ vs time obtained were almost parallel and linear beyond two half-lives of the reaction showing the zero order dependence of reaction on IO_4^- . The slope of concentration-time plots are taken as zero order rate constant⁴ (k_0) and reproducible within $\pm 4\%$. The rates were increased with increase of DMA as well as Os^{VIII} concentrations. The plot of $\log k_0$ vs $\log [\text{DMA}]$ was found linear and showed fractional (0.5) order with respect to $[\text{DMA}]$. The plot of $\log k_0$ vs $\log [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ was found to be linear and showed the order with respect to $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ as unity. Similar plots showed that at lower alkali concentrations, the order with respect to $[\text{OH}^-]$ is fractional (ca. 0.5) while at higher alkali concentration (> 0.20 mol dm^{-3}) the order with respect to $[\text{OH}^-]$ were found to be sensitive

negligibly small increase in the reaction rate. Variation of dielectric constant of the reaction medium by varying the content of t-butanol (upto 30%, v/v) showed no effect on the reaction rate. Initially added products HCOONa , NH_4OH and KIO_3 each upto 4.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} showed no effect on the reaction rate.

Kinetic runs were carried at $[\text{DMA}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2}$, $[\text{IO}_4^-] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$, $[\text{OH}^-] = 0.20$ mol dm^{-3} for catalysed and uncatalysed reactions. At 298, 303, 308 and 313 K, the catalysed reaction with 3.2×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} Os^{VIII} resulted k_0 as 1.0, 1.5, 1.9 and 2.6×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} s^{-1} and the uncatalysed reaction resulted k_0 as 0.7, 1.0, 1.6 and 2.6×10^{-8} mol dm^{-3} s^{-1} . From the plot of $\log (k_0/T)$ vs $1/T$, enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) for the catalysed and uncatalysed reactions were obtained as 47.9 ± 3 and 81.4 ± 4 kJ mol^{-1} respectively, and the corresponding values of average entropy of activation (ΔS^*) were -218 ± 12 and -136 ± 8 JK⁻¹ mol^{-1} and free energy of activation (ΔG^*) values 114 ± 5 and 123 ± 6 kJ mol^{-1} .

The results of the study on the Os^{VIII} -catalysed reaction are in agreement with the complex formation between catalyst and substrate followed by decomposition of complex in slow step. Further, it is followed by other fast steps to yield the products. Attempts to obtain a spectral evidence for the complex involvement in the reaction failed. However, the interaction may be feeble; such complex formation between catalyst and the substrate has also been observed in other studies^{4,5} and the probable structure of the complex is as follows.

The evidence for the complex formation is restricted to kinetic data (see *infra*). All the experimental results are in agreement with that shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Scheme 1 leads to the rate law (5)

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{d[\text{IO}_4^-]}{dt} = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{DMA}]_T [\text{OH}^-]_T [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_T}{1 + K_1 K_2 [\text{DMA}]_T [\text{OH}^-]_T + K_1 [\text{OH}^-]_T} \quad (5)$$

Strictly the factors $\{1 + K_1 [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]\}$ and $\{1 + K_2 [\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]\}$ should also be in the denominator in the right-hand-side of equation (5). But in view of low concentration of Os^{VIII} used, the terms approximated to unity. According to equation (5), the plots of $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_T/\text{rate}$ vs $[\text{OH}^-]_T^{-1}$ and $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]_T/\text{rate}$ vs $[\text{DMA}]_T^{-1}$ should be linear, and which was found to be such. From the slope and intercept the values of K_1 , K_2 and k at 25° were found to be $6.8 \pm 3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $120 \pm 5 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $0.48 \pm 0.05 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. The value of K_1 being in agreement with the value reported by Bhatt *et al.*⁶, indicates that the osmium(VIII) species, $\text{OsO}_4(\text{OH}_2)^{2-}$ and $\text{OsO}_5(\text{OH})^{3-}$ are in equilibrium and $\text{OsO}_5(\text{OH})^{3-}$ is the active form of catalyst. Using these values, the rates, over a range of conditions, were calculated and compared with the experimental data (Table 1). There is good agreement.

The negligibly small effects of ionic strength

and dielectric constant on the reaction rates are presumably due to the fact that the reaction is between a neutral and a charged species. Osmium(VIII) catalyses the reaction by the decrease of activation energy as observed by comparing the enthalpy of activation values for the catalysed and uncatalysed reactions.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING $[\text{IO}_4^-]$, $[\text{DMA}]$, $[\text{OH}^-]$ and $[\text{Os}^{\text{VIII}}]$ ON THE Os^{VIII} -CATALYSED IO_4^- OXIDATION OF DMA

Temp. = 25° , $I = 0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KCl)

[DMA] mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [IO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	[OH ⁻] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁶ [Os ^{VIII}] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁷ k _o (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	
				Exptl.	Calcd.
0.5	4.0	0.20	3.2	4.2	3.9
1.0	4.0	0.20	3.2	7.0	6.2
2.0	4.0	0.20	3.2	9.2	8.9
3.0	4.0	0.20	3.2	10.5	10.6
5.0	4.0	0.20	3.2	12.8	11.9
2.0	1.0	0.20	3.2	8.8	8.9
2.0	2.0	0.20	3.2	9.4	8.9
2.0	4.0	0.20	3.2	9.2	8.9
2.0	6.0	0.20	3.2	9.4	8.9
2.0	10.0	0.20	3.2	9.0	8.9
2.0	4.0	0.02	3.2	3.6	3.4
2.0	4.0	0.04	3.2	5.2	5.2
2.0	4.0	0.08	3.2	7.0	7.0
2.0	4.0	0.12	3.2	8.0	8.0
2.0	4.0	0.20	3.2	9.2	8.9
2.0	4.0	0.28	3.2	10.2	9.4
2.0	4.0	0.20	0.87	2.8	2.4
2.0	4.0	0.20	2.6	7.5	7.2
2.0	4.0	0.20	3.2	9.2	8.9
2.0	4.0	0.20	3.5	10.0	9.8
2.0	4.0	0.20	4.4	12.5	12.3
2.0	4.0	0.20	7.0	18.5	19.5

Error = $\pm 5\%$.

Evidence for Os^{VI}: In a separate experiment, DMA ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and OsO_4 ($2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) were mixed in alkaline medium. The colour due to OsO_4 in alkaline medium disappeared. After acidification the mixture was titrated with standard Ce^{IV} . The consumption of 2 moles of Ce^{IV} per mole of OsO_4 indicated the presence of lower oxidation state of Os as Os^{VI} . This was also confirmed spectroscopically by comparing the electronic spectra of DMA, Os^{VIII} and their mixture in equivalent concentrations in alkaline medium. It was observed that the spectra of the mixture is

similar to that of Os^{VI} in alkaline medium. Further, on addition of excess of periodate to the mixture, the spectra showed that Os^{VIII} was regenerated.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals and double-distilled water were used throughout the study. The periodate solution was standardised iodometrically⁴. Standardised and freshly diluted solution of dimethylamine (40%) was used. The Os^{VIII} solutions were made by dissolving OsO_4 (Johnson Matthey) in NaOH (0.5 mol dm^{-3}). The concentration was ascertained⁷ by addition of excess hexacyanoferrate(II) followed by titration of unreacted hexacyanoferrate(II) with standard Ce^{IV} solution in acid medium. KCl and KOH were used to maintain required ionic strength and alkalinity respectively.

A Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer was used.

Kinetic measurement : All kinetic runs were carried out at a constant temperature ($25 \pm 0.1^\circ$) unless otherwise mentioned. The reaction was initiated by mixing previously thermostated solutions containing required quantities of DMA, KOH , KCl and Os^{VIII} with required quantity of thermostated IO_4^- solution. The reaction was followed by determining gross concentration of IO_4^- iodometrically at neutral pH maintained by phosphate buffer.

The products formate and ammonia were found by spot test⁸ and Nessler's reagent⁹ respectively. When DMA was in excess, ammonia, formate and formaldehyde were found as main products. Thus the oxidation of DMA takes place in two steps with formaldehyde as the intermediate,

As the order of reaction with respect to oxidant, substrate and OH^- being different for oxidation of formaldehyde than the over all oxidation of DMA failed in treating this reaction as consecutive according to Frost and Pearson¹⁰.

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